

BUILD-project

**D 4.3 Report on PPI simulations &
consolidated training approach and
update training material for
procurers**

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BUILD

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Executive Summary

Scope

This report focuses on innovative public procurement practices, emphasizing capacity-building activities aimed at public procurers across Europe. It highlights the efforts made in fostering innovation through knowledge sharing, training, and staff exchanges. The objective is to enhance the procurement processes in public institutions, driving innovation and improving procurement outcomes. The project involved three key cities—Tartu, Rotterdam, and Turku—working collaboratively to strengthen their procurement capabilities.

The report outlines key activities, including training sessions, staff exchanges, and mutual learning opportunities, which are aimed at equipping public procurers with the skills and knowledge needed to stimulate innovative procurement practices. Special attention was given to areas such as market consultations, risk assessment, and citizen participation in the procurement process.

Methodology

Several work packages were developed and executed to achieve the project's goals:

Training of Public Procurers (Work Package 4.1):

This involved a webinar and hands-on training sessions designed to enhance the skills of public procurers. The focus was on innovative procurement strategies and techniques.

Staff Exchanges to Stimulate Mutual Learning (Work Package 4.2):

Staff exchanges among the cities of Tartu, Rotterdam, and Turku were organized to promote knowledge sharing and collaboration. These exchanges enabled the cities to learn from each other's procurement services, with a particular focus on market consultations, innovation-stimulating procurement methods, citizen participation, and risk management.

Results

The activities outlined in this report have resulted in increased collaboration between the participating cities, leading to more effective and innovative procurement practices. The shared learning experiences have been particularly valuable in highlighting new approaches to procurement that prioritize innovation and public engagement. Each city has reported enhanced capacity and readiness to implement innovative procurement methods.

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1. Objective of the *Work package 4.3 PPI Simulation, Consolidated Training Approach and Updated Training materials and task*

This report summarizes the activities that allow public buyers to simulate the entire innovation procurement life cycle. These activities build on the work done in Work Package 2, Task 2.2 Enhancing the Interest of Enterprises in Innovation Procurements, Work Package 4.1 Training of Public Procurers and Work Package 4.2, Staff Exchanges to Stimulate Mutual Learning. These materials are available on the project website. This report summarizing all activities, is set to be published by Month 24 (M24).

2. Planning

The planning for this work package was informed by key insights from Work Package 4.1, Training of Public Procurers; Work Package 4.2, Staff Exchanges to Stimulate Mutual Learning; and workshops conducted under Work Package 2, Task 2.2, Enhancing the Interest of Enterprises in Innovation Procurements. We compiled the knowledge from these work packages to develop new materials, which are outlined in the subheading below.

A key realization during this project was the importance of practical, real-life examples, so we have incorporated these into the training material. This work package provides a concise summary of the lessons learned throughout the project. While it doesn't cover every detail, it offers valuable guidance for public procurers considering innovative procurement methods but unsure of how to stimulate innovation effectively.

The development of the materials for this work package involved the creation of two informative posters and an online presentation, simulating PPI processes and giving practical examples through best-cases. The first poster serves as an introduction to innovative public procurement, while the second provides a concise summary of key elements learned throughout the project. Both posters were designed using Microsoft Word and converted into PDFs for easy viewing and accessibility. Their clear and succinct format ensures that public procurers can quickly grasp the essential concepts of innovative procurement.

The posters:

4.3. Introduction

What are innovative procurements about?

Public procurements are a significant tool for generating new innovations and business opportunities. They play a crucial role in achieving Europe's goals related to climate, the circular economy, and innovation policy. The funds allocated to procurements represent a major force for change, which can either strengthen or weaken the green transition.

Innovative procurement refers to the acquisition of a new or significantly improved product or service, which can enhance the productivity, quality, sustainability, and impact of public services.

Why do we need innovative procurements?

Challenging old patterns is necessary to address issues related to costs, sustainability, or well-being. Innovative procurements are needed to solve new types of challenges in situations where, for example, the current product or service no longer works, the set goals require broader collaboration or new approaches, or when environmental changes encourage the search for new solutions.

In public sector procurement, it's possible to pilot completely new approaches—considering productivity, efficiency, quality, and sustainability. At the same time, these procurements can boost the development and competitiveness of businesses. Innovations can also improve the quality of public services under the pressure of rising costs.

What makes something innovative?

A public procurement is considered innovative when new practices are introduced in the planning of the procurement, in the procurement procedure itself, or in the definition of the procurement target. For example, instead of a predefined implementation model, the procurer may focus its procurement on desired outcomes and impacts, giving suppliers more freedom to propose alternative solutions.

A procurement target is innovative when it involves a completely new or significantly improved product or service. The procurement target or solution may be innovative for the procuring organization, even if it has already been implemented elsewhere. Innovation can manifest as a new solution for the contracting entity, even if it's already in use by other organizations or industries.

What really matters?

Innovative procurements are about more than just a single new procurement procedure—they involve new goal-setting and solutions to issues that cannot be solved through traditional means. The methods and procurement process are determined by the objectives and needs—not the other way around.

More important than novelty is that innovative procurement leads to a better outcome for the client or end-user. This improvement might manifest as lower life-cycle costs, higher customer satisfaction, improved quality, or enhanced cost efficiency.

Developing sustainable and innovative procurements is an ongoing effort that never truly comes to an end: markets evolve, new solutions become available, and needs change, alongside continuous growth in researched knowledge.

Figure 1 - Poster on Introduction to PPI

4.3. Lessons learned by BUILD

We need innovations when conventional solutions are no longer sufficient.

- When the current product or service is not working as needed
- When the complex strategic goals demand for new solutions
- When the market has new solutions to offer that doesn't fit to the previous tendering
- When the operational environment has changed

We are facing global challenges concerning welfare and environment.

Innovations can be piloted in the public sector – taking productivity, efficiency, quality and sustainability into account. At the same time, the development and competitiveness of companies will be accelerated.

Here are some lessons learned when procuring innovations:

1 Innovation procurement starts by taking the time to define the actual need

- It is important to think in good time whether the familiar solution still meets the current need, or is it worth developing new innovation or innovative approach?
- Preliminary market dialogue is helpful when adjusting the planned procurement process and/or the object of the procurement
- Make sure, you have sufficient input from end-users and clients and all relevant sectors within the city and possible interest groups

2 Market information is a valuable part of procurement preparation – also when choosing the procedure

- generate a realistic picture of the maturity of the solution and whether it is possible to obtain competitive offers that meet your need
- A procurement procedure involving development work makes it possible to specify the final product or service together with the market. However, negotiated procedures often take time, and sometimes a thorough market dialogue can also lead to the same outcome, allowing the procurement itself to be carried out as an open procedure.
- Procuring an experiment/pilot can also be seen as the acquisition of information, as the goal of an experiment is often to obtain information rather than a ready-made service.

3 Make an effort to ensure that the bidders have an incentive to participate and invest their time and knowhow

- It is worth considering whether the remuneration paid to the participants in a negotiation procedure would generate savings in the long term in the form of commitment.
- When the purchased service is paid according to effectiveness, it encourages the service provider to think carefully about what kind of model leads to the desired results.
- Value-based procurement is suitable when it is possible to verify the obtained effects

4 Acquiring innovations always involves risks, and in the end it is a question of finding a balance between the risks and the desired benefits

- Procurement models based on phased progress can often help manage risks.
- Risk management is about knowing the need, the field of actors and the situation well and being on time. Cooperation between clients and sharing practices is also important so that risks can be better anticipated together in the future

5 Procurement units that are not afraid of development work are needed to bring new solutions to the market

- Bringing a new solution to the market helps to cut costs in the long term, even though development costs are considerable – whether it is a single development purchase or a long negotiation process.

When procuring innovations, you need to start early.
Time and effort in the beginning rewards in the end.

Figure 2 - Poster of lessons learned by the BUILD experience

In addition to the posters, the material addressing market consultations, citizen participation, procurement methods that boost innovation, and risk assessment was developed using Microsoft Sway. This online platform allows for the creation of visually appealing presentations that can be easily shared. By utilizing Sway, we ensured that the content is accessible to anyone with internet access and the link, eliminating the need for downloads and enhancing user convenience.

[The link to the Sway presentation](#), along with the downloadable posters, are featured on the BUILD webpage, making it straightforward for public procurers to access these resources.

2.1 Results from workshops

The workshops conducted for public procurers (Work Package 2, Task 2.2, Enhancing the Interest of Enterprises in Innovation Procurements) yielded valuable insights into the challenges and needs associated with conducting innovative public procurements. The detailed results from the workshops can be found in Deliverable 2.2 Report on Market Consultation Activities. Participants identified several key factors necessary for success. A common theme was the need for additional time and financial resources to fully support the complexities involved in innovative procurement processes. Public procurers expressed that while there is a desire to implement innovative approaches, practical barriers such as insufficient funding and tight timelines often limit their ability to do so effectively.

Moreover, participants highlighted the necessity of real-life examples to better understand how innovation can be integrated into procurement. Case studies or success stories from other entities were seen as crucial in building the confidence needed to take calculated risks in procurement strategies. Another important takeaway was the need for continuous training. Procurers emphasized that more frequent and focused training sessions would enhance their skills and familiarity with innovative procurement methods.

In addition to practical tools, participants stressed the need for a supportive community. A proposed idea was the creation of a forum or platform where public procurers could discuss issues, share experiences, and explore possibilities related to innovative procurements. This kind of peer-to-peer exchange would foster learning, encourage experimentation, and provide a space to address challenges collaboratively.

Based on the insights gathered from these workshops, we developed a set of materials specifically designed to address these identified needs. These materials incorporate real-life examples of innovative procurement processes, such as market consultations and citizen participation, to provide concrete guidance on how to proceed. In addition, they include examples of risk assessments and highlight a few procurement methods that can help boost innovation.

The materials can serve as a training tool or a checklist for public procurers, offering guidance when they are uncertain about how to initiate an innovative procurement or if they feel stuck at any stage of the process. While the materials contain practical, real-world examples, they are also supplemented with theoretical frameworks to provide a deeper understanding of the concepts at play. This dual approach ensures that public procurers have both the inspiration and the practical tools necessary to successfully implement innovative procurement strategies.

2.2 Results from international and national trainings

National training held in Turku, Finland

The results from the Training of Public Procurers played a pivotal role in shaping the material developed for Work Package 4.3, which focuses on aspects of innovative procurements. The training sessions revealed that public procurers not only seek practical tools for implementing innovative procurement processes, but also have a strong interest in real-life examples. These examples help build confidence, showing that innovative procurement is feasible and often less risky when others have successfully navigated similar paths.

During the training sessions, case studies from various EU cities were presented, showcasing innovative public procurement practices. These examples illustrated the value of market consultations, highlighted procurement methods designed to foster innovation—such as negotiation procedures and innovation partnerships—and underscored the importance of conducting thorough risk assessments. These elements consistently emerged as key features in the most innovative procurements examined during the training.

National training held in Tartu, Estonia

In response to the insights gathered from these sessions, the material developed for Work Package 4.3 integrates both theoretical frameworks and real-life examples. The content covers practical guidance on market consultations, procurement methods that promote innovation, and strategies for risk assessment. By including these components, the material serves as a comprehensive resource for public procurers, offering not only theoretical knowledge but also practical, tested solutions to aid in the adoption of innovative procurement strategies.

National training held in Rotterdam, The Netherlands

2.3 Results from the staff exchanges

The staff exchanges conducted under Work Package 4.2 provided critical insights that informed the development of the material for Work Package 4.3. During these exchanges, the cities of Tartu, Rotterdam, and Turku shared their procurement practices, focusing on how each city approaches innovative procurement. These exchanges offered a platform for mutual learning, allowing participants to discuss their organizational structures, strategies for stimulating innovation, and specific challenges they face.

Staff exchange in Turku, Finland

A few key themes emerged consistently throughout the exchanges: market consultations, procurement methods designed to promote innovation, citizen participation, and risk assessment. These topics were highlighted by all participating cities as essential elements of a successful innovative procurement process. The staff exchanges included in-depth discussions, where participants shared examples from their own cities, described the hurdles they encountered, and showcased solutions they had implemented to boost innovation in their procurement processes.

In planning Work Package 4.3, we utilized the information gathered from these exchanges, incorporating the most frequently discussed and emphasized topics. These included practical guidance on market consultations, innovative procurement methods, citizen involvement, and risk assessment. The material reflects the shared experiences and best practices exchanged among the cities, providing a well-rounded resource for public procurers to apply in their own work.

Staff exchange in Tartu, Estonia

The staff exchanges, which were originally shaped by feedback from personnel through workshops and questionnaires, revealed a strong desire for practical examples and a clearer understanding of how to address common challenges in procurement. These challenges included managing time and budget constraints, engaging stakeholders, and effectively recognizing opportunities for innovation. By addressing these core issues, the exchanges helped shape the content of Work Package 4.3, ensuring that the material includes both theoretical knowledge and practical tools to help public procurers overcome the hurdles they face when pursuing innovative procurement strategies.

Staff exchange in Rotterdam, The Netherlands

2.4 Target groups

This work package and its accompanying materials are designed for individuals involved in public procurement, particularly those looking to adopt more innovative approaches. It aims to provide practical guidance and strategies for enhancing procurement processes and fostering innovation. While primarily targeted at public sector professionals, the insights may also be useful for private buyers. Although private buyers are not bound by public procurement laws or citizen participation requirements, the methods outlined here can still offer valuable ideas for boosting innovation in their procurement practices.

3. Content of the material

Based on the insights gathered throughout the project, this work package focuses on several key topics: market consultation, citizen participation, innovative procurement methods, and risk assessment. These areas were selected because they consistently emerged as critical elements during the workshops, trainings, and staff exchanges.

One of the most emphasized topics that came up in the workshops was the need for authentic and effective market consultations. Companies highly value these opportunities to engage with public buyers, and public procurers expressed a strong interest in conducting more of them, though they are often limited by time and resource constraints.

In addition, citizen participation, procurement methods that foster innovation, and risk assessment were identified as crucial components during international and national trainings, as well as through real-life examples. During staff exchanges, cities shared their approaches to implementing innovative procurement, demonstrating how these practices are put into action within different municipal contexts.

3.1 Market consultation

Market consultations are vital in public procurement, allowing authorities to engage with the market before launching a tender. They ensure procurement strategies are informed and aligned with market conditions. By consulting potential suppliers and stakeholders, teams can refine their approaches and identify innovative solutions.

3.2 Citizen participation

Citizen participation is crucial in innovative public procurement, enabling communities to influence the goods and services that impact them. Engaging citizens ensures outcomes align with community needs and introduces diverse perspectives that drive innovation. While it requires careful planning, citizen participation enhances transparency, builds public support, and can lead to innovative solutions.

3.3 Boosting innovation through procurement methods

Choosing the right procurement method is vital for fostering innovation in public procurement. Different methods provide unique advantages for encouraging creative solutions and meeting complex needs. The appropriate approach can stimulate the market, promote collaboration with suppliers, and yield effective, cutting-edge solutions.

3.4 Risk assessment

Risk assessment is essential in public procurement, focusing on identifying and mitigating potential risks throughout the process. Effective risk management ensures projects are completed on time and within budget.

In innovative public procurement, where solutions and methods may be untested, risk assessment is even more critical. The uncertainties involved can include unproven technologies or new service models. By conducting thorough assessments, public authorities can proactively address challenges and minimize the impact of unforeseen issues, ultimately enhancing the likelihood of successfully implementing innovative solutions.

4. Collective learnings / summary

Work Package 4.3 focuses on developing practical resources to support public procurers in implementing innovative procurement methods. Building on insights from previous work packages—specifically Work Package 4.1 (Training of Public Procurers), Work Package 4.2 (Staff Exchanges), and workshops—this package emphasizes the importance of real-life examples and accessible information.

The materials produced include two informative posters: one introducing innovative public procurement and another summarizing key elements learned throughout the project. Additionally, an online presentation created using Microsoft Sway provides detailed information on essential topics such as market consultations, citizen participation, procurement methods that boost innovation, and risk assessment. These resources are designed to be easily accessible, ensuring that public procurers can readily utilize them in their efforts.

Key learnings from this work package highlight the necessity of practical examples to build confidence among procurers, the significance of engaging citizens to ensure alignment with community needs, and the importance of selecting appropriate procurement methods to foster innovation. Furthermore, effective risk assessment is crucial for navigating the uncertainties associated with innovative projects.

Through this work package, we aim to empower public authorities to navigate the complexities of innovative procurement effectively, fostering collaboration and creativity while meeting the evolving needs of the community.